

Deliverable D-JRP21-WP6.3

Workpackage 6

Responsible partners: BfR, SVA

Contributing partners: BfR, VFL/EMU,
PIWET

GENERAL INFORMATION

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BIOPIGEE

Workshop 1 completed

BIOPIGEE Task 6.3 lead/deputy

BfR (DE), SVA (SE)

Contributing institutes (Dissemination activity at national events)

BfR (DE), VFL/EMU (EE), PIWET (PL)

BIOPIGEE project

The zoonotic pathogens *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus can cause acute and chronic diseases in humans. The most common transmission route is assumed to be foodborn from pigs. The aim of the project BIOPIGEE “Biosecurity practices for pig farming across Europe” of the One Health European Joint Programme is to identify effective and cost-efficient biosecurity measures for the reduction of these pathogens in the pig production chain in order to prevent human infections. To achieve this, different literature reviews, field studies, experiments and transmission/cost modelling are carried out. Finally, it is the aim to inform stakeholders like farmers, veterinarians, authorities and the pig industry about the findings on best biosecurity practice.

Background and objective of Workshop 1

The first workshop was originally planned to gather input from stakeholders and to inform about the project within the first half year of the project. Due to the covid 19 pandemic, the implementation of the event was delayed and changed to a format of several small national, partly online events to connect researchers with stakeholders. The objective of activity at these national (online) events was to extract, inform about and discuss effectiveness of biosecurity measures and to rate country-specific biosecurity practices, also to exchange ideas about how to disseminate findings to stakeholders (e.g. farmers and veterinarians).

German event

In November 2021 (25th-26th), a 2-days-hybrid event of the North Rhine-Westphalian Pig Health Service took place at the Chamber of Agriculture in Bad Sassendorf. Here, news on currently relevant diseases, preventive measures and animal welfare issues were exchanged in presentations and discussions as well as in breaks between sessions with a wide audience of veterinarians, representatives of agriculture and industry, laboratory staff and researchers (approx. 100 participants). The results of the BIOPIGEE project were presented by E. Burow (BfR). During the event, a contact was made with an advisory service on biosecurity practices in pig production in Baden-Wuerttemberg, and in a subsequent telephone meeting information was exchanged in more detail on measure effectiveness

and the interest and use of farmers to implement knowledge. Another network was established with the agricultural education centre of the North Rhine-Westphalian Chamber of Agriculture and a web meeting was arranged after the conference to discuss how best to disseminate project results to agricultural students. Further exchange was agreed.

Estonian event

In March 2022 (2nd-3rd) the annual conference of the Institute of the Veterinary Medicine and Animal Sciences of the Estonian University of Life Sciences 'Healthy Animal – Healthy Food' gathering the farmers, food industry representatives, and state officials of the field took place (more than 200 participants). The results of the BIOPIGEE research were presented and discussed in two presentations in two sections of the event.

On May 12, 2022, a seminar took place for the animal health officials from the headquarter and regional offices of the Agriculture and Food Board (27 participants). The seminar was organized by the Estonian Veterinary and Food Laboratory (VFL) and the results of the BIOPIGEE project were introduced.

Polish event

In November 2021 (26th-27th) the XVI Congress of the Polish Society of Veterinary Sciences was held (<http://xvi-kongres-ptnw.wmw.sggw.pl/>). The hybrid event hosted 495 participants, representing academia, diagnostics, and veterinary practice. In line with the motto of the congress „Omnia Autem Animalia Sunt”, the proceedings were conducted in 17 thematic sessions. Altogether 26 plenary lectures and 357 communications were presented. The oral presentation entitled “BIOPIGEE project: *Salmonella* occurrence in pig farms” was presented within the session on swine physiology and pathology. The national results of the project, focusing on the frequency of infections and responsible *Salmonella* serovars, gained the interest of the participants in the light of divergence from a low clinical manifestation of the disease.

Benefit from the workshops

These national events were a good platform to inform about the BIOPIGEE project and results, and to exchange ideas. New contacts were made that may be of help for the dissemination of gathered knowledge in the project.

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